

EQUATION OF THE DERIVATIVE OF THE FUNCTION TO SOLVE EQUATIONS

Tillabayev B.Sh.

Fergana Politechnical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7346610>*Abstract.* This article presents approximate calculations using the exact integral*Keywords:* integral, equality, inequality.

УРАВНЕНИЕ ПРОИЗВОДНОЙ ФУНКЦИИ ДЛЯ РЕШЕНИЯ УРАВНЕНИЙ

Аннотация. В данной статье представлены приближенные расчеты с использованием точного интеграла*Ключевые слова:* интеграл, равенство, неравенство.

INTRODUCTION

Let us be given a non-standard equation in the form of some kind of $f(x) = 0$ in section $[a, b]$. Let it be required to find the solution of this equation in Section $[a, b]$ (if it exists) ε in accuracy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

First of all, we check whether the function $f(x)$ satisfies the conditions of Baltsano-Cauchy theorem 1 in the section $[a, b]$ or not.

Theorem one of Balsano-Koshi. If the function $f(x)$ is defined on the section $[a, b]$ and is continuous and has different sign value at the extreme points of the interval, then there exists a point $c \in (a, b)$ such that $f(c) = 0$.

So, if the function $f(x)$ fulfills the conditions of the theorem, then the section $[a, b]$ contains the solution of the equation $f(x) = 0$.

RESULTS

Suppose that the section $[a, b]$ contains the root of the equation $f(x) = 0$. That is, let $x \in [a, b]$ exist such that $f(x) = 0$ is equal. Also let $x = a + \Delta x$ be. Then the equality $f(a + \Delta x) = 0$ holds. If we consider the equation $f(x_0 + \Delta x) \approx f(x_0) + f'(x_0) \cdot \Delta x$,

$$f(a + \Delta x) \approx f(a) + f'(a) \cdot \Delta x \approx 0 \text{ equality, that is, } \Delta x \approx -\frac{f(a)}{f'(a)} \text{ is formed. From}$$

this, if we consider the equality $\Delta x = a - x$,

$$x - a \approx -\frac{f(a)}{f'(a)}, \quad x \approx a - \frac{f(a)}{f'(a)} \text{ equalities are formed.}$$

If the equality $\left| -\frac{f(a)}{f'(a)} \right| < \varepsilon$ is fulfilled, the solution of the equation will be found

approximately with accuracy ε .

Suppose that this inequality does not hold, then we denote $a - \frac{f(a)}{f'(a)}$ by x_1 and consider the equation in the interval $[x_1, b]$. Denote the root of the equation as $x = x_1 + \Delta x$ and calculate $x \approx x_1 - \frac{f(x_1)}{f'(x_1)}$. If we denote it as x_2 and $|x_2 - x_1| < \varepsilon$ then $x_1 + \Delta x$ is the root. Continuing in this way, after a finite step, the inequality $|x_n - x_{n-1}| < \varepsilon$ is satisfied and x_n is taken to be an approximate solution of the given equation around ε .

Example 1. Prove that the equation $f(x) = x^3 - 3x - 6$ has a unique solution in the interval $[2;3]$ and find it with precision 0.001.

DISCUSSION

Solving. $f(x) = x^3 - 3x - 6$ is a function defined on the interval $[2;3]$, continuous and $f(2) = -4 < 0$, $f(3) = 12 > 0$. On the other hand $\forall x \in (2;3)$ for $f'(x) = 3(x^2 - 1) > 0$, that is, the function is increasing. Therefore, the equation $x^3 - 3x - 6 = 0$ has a unique solution in the interval $[2;3]$. Now let's say $x = 2 + \Delta x$ and find Δx such that $f(x) = f(2 + \Delta x) = 0$. For sufficiently small Δx

$$f(2 + \Delta x) = f(2) + \Delta f(2) \approx f(2) + f'(2) \cdot \Delta x.$$

Then we come to the equation $f(2) + f'(2) \cdot \Delta x \approx 0$. By finding $\Delta x \approx -\frac{f(2)}{f'(2)}$ from

this, we find the equation $x = 2 + \Delta x \approx 2 - \frac{f(2)}{f'(2)}$ for the solution. Finally, taking into account

that $f(2) = -4$, $f'(2) = (3x^2 - 3)|_{x=2} = 9$, we find $x \approx x_1 = 2 - \frac{-4}{9} = 2.4$. Using the same reasoning, we find the solution:

$$x_2 = 2.4 - \frac{f(2.4)}{f'(2.4)} = 2.4 - \frac{0.62}{14.28} \approx 2.360, \quad |x_2 - x_1| = 0.40 > 0.001;$$

$$x_3 = 2.360 - \frac{f(2.360)}{f'(2.360)} \approx 2.356, \quad |x_3 - x_2| = 0.004 > 0.001;$$

$$x_4 = 2.356 - \frac{f(2.356)}{f'(2.356)} \approx 2.356, \quad |x_4 - x_3| = 0.000 < 0.001.$$

CONCLUSION

Therefore, the number 2.356 is the solution of the equation with an accuracy of 0.001.

REFERENCES

1. Shavkatjon o'g'li, T. B. (2022). Proving The Inequalities Using a Definite Integral and Series. *Texas Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 13, 64-68.
2. Shavkatjon o'g'li, T. B. (2022). SOME INTEGRAL EQUATIONS FOR A MULTIVARIABLE FUNCTION. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(4), 160-163.
3. Рашидов, Ю. К., Орзиматов, Ж. Т., Эсонов, О. О. Ё., & Зайнабидинова, М. И. К. (2022). СОЛНЕЧНЫЙ ВОЗДУХОНАГРЕВАТЕЛЬ С ВОЗДУХОПРОНИЦАЕМЫМ МАТРИЧНЫМ АБСОРБЕРОМ. *Scientific progress*, 3(4), 1237-1244.
4. Усаров, М. К., and Г. И. Маматисаев. "Вынужденные колебания коробчатой конструкции панельных зданий при динамических воздействиях." *Проблемы механики* 2 (2010): 23-25.
5. Usmonova, N. A., & Khudaykulov, S. I. (2021, April). SPATIAL CAVERNS IN FLOWS WITH THEIR PERTURBATIONS IMPACT ON THE SAFETY OF THE KARKIDON RESERVOIR. In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 126-130).
6. Усаров, Махаматали Корабоевич, and Гиёсиддин Илхомидинович Маматисаев. "КОЛЕБАНИЯ КОРОБЧАТОЙ КОНСТРУКЦИИ КРУПНОПАНЕЛЬНЫХ ЗДАНИЙ ПРИ ДИНАМИЧЕСКИХ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЯХ." *Научный форум: технические и физико-математические науки*. 2019.
7. Madaliev, M. E. U., Maksudov, R. I., Mullaev, I. I., Abdullaev, B. K., & Haidarov, A. R. (2021). Investigation of the Influence of the Computational Grid for Turbulent Flow. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 18, 111-118.
8. Hamdamalievich S. A. Determination of the deposition of particles contained in the water passing through the sump well // *Central asian journal of theoretical & applied sciences*. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 244-251.
9. Hamdamalievich S. A., Nurmuhammad H. Analysis of Heat Transfer of Solar Water Collectors // *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*. – 2021. – Т. 18. – С. 60-65.
10. ugli Mo'minov, O. A., Maqsudov, R. I., & qizi Abdukhalilova, S. B. (2021). Analysis of Convective Finns to Increase the Efficiency of Radiators used in Heating Systems. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 18, 84-89.
11. Maqsudov, R. I., & qizi Abdukhalilova, S. B. (2021). Improving Support for the Process of the Thermal Convection Process by Installing. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 18, 56-59.
12. Madaliev, E. U., & qizi Abdukhalilova, S. B. (2022). Repair of Water Networks. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCES*, 3(5), 389-394.
13. Malikov, Z. M., & Madaliev, E. U. (2019). Mathematical simulation of the speeds of ideally newtonovsky, incompressible, viscous liquid on a curvilinearly smoothed pipe site. *Scientific-technical journal*, 22(3), 64-73.
14. Мадхадимов, М. М., Абдулхаев, З. Э., & Сатторов, А. Х. (2018). Регулирования работы центробежных насосов с изменением частота вращения. *Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире*, (12-1), 83-88.
15. Mo'minov, O. A. O'tbosarov Sh. R. "Theoretical analysis of the ventilation emitters used in low-temperature heat supply systems, and heat production of these emitters" *Eurasian journal of academic research*, 495-497.

16. Рашидов, Ю. К., Орзиматов, Ж. Т., & Исмоилов, М. М. (2019). Воздушные солнечные коллекторы: перспективы применения в условиях Узбекистана. *ББК 20.1 я43 Э 40*.
17. Abobakirovich, A. B., Sodikovich, A. Y., & Ogli, M. I. I. (2019). Optimization of operating parameters of flat solar air heaters. *Вестник науки и образования*, (19-2 (73)), 6-9.
18. Abbasov, Y. S., & ugli Usmonov, M. A. (2022). Design of an Effective Heating System for Residential and Public Buildings. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCES*, 3(5), 341-346.
19. Usmonova, N. A. (2021). Structural Characteristics of the Cavern at a Fine Bubbled Stage of Cavitation. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 18, 95-101.
20. Nasirov Ismail Azizovich. On The Accuracy of the Finite Element Method on the Example of Problems about Natural Oscillations. *EUROPEAN MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF MODERN SCIENCE* <https://emjms.academicjournal.io>
21. Nosirov A.A., Nasirov I.A. Simulation of Spatial Own of Vibrations of Axisymmetric Structures *EUROPEAN MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF MODERN SCIENCE* <https://emjms.academicjournal.io>
22. Xamdaliyevich, S. A., & Rahmankulov, S. A. (2021, July). Investigation of heat transfer processes of solar water, air contact collector. In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 161-165).
23. Madaliev, M. E. U., Rakhmankulov, S. A., & Tursunaliyev, M. M. U. (2021). Comparison of Finite-Difference Schemes for the Burgers Problem. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 18, 76-83
24. Abdullayev, B. X., & Rahmankulov, S. A. (2021). Modeling Aeration in High Pressure Hydraulic Circulation. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCES*, 2(12), 127-136.
25. Abdukarimov, B. A., O'tbosarov, S. R., & Tursunaliyev, M. M. (2014). Increasing Performance Efficiency by Investigating the Surface of the Solar Air Heater Collector. *NM Safarov and A. Alinazarov. Use of environmentally friendly energy sources*.
26. Rashidov, Y. K., & Ramankulov, S. A. (2021). Improving the Efficiency of Flat Solar Collectors in Heat Supply Systems. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCES*, 2(12), 152-159
27. Madraximov, M. M., Nurmuxammad, X., & Abdulkhaev, Z. E. (2021, November). Hydraulic Calculation Of Jet Pump Performance Improvement. In *International Conference On Multidisciplinary Research And Innovative Technologies (Vol. 2, pp. 20-24)*.
28. Akramov, A. A. U., & Nomonov, M. B. U. (2022). Improving the Efficiency Account Hydraulic of Water Supply Sprinklers. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 3(6), 364-370.
29. Умурзакова, М. А., Усмонов, М. А., & Рахимов, М. Н. (2021). АНАЛОГИЯ РЕЙНОЛЬДСА ПРИ ТЕЧЕНИЯХ В ДИФФУЗОРНО-КОНФУЗОРНЫХ КАНАЛАХ. *Экономика и социум*, (3-2), 479-486.
30. Сагторов, А. Х., Акромов, А. А. У., & Абдуразаков, А. М. (2020). Повышение эффективности калорифера, используемого в системе вентиляции. *Достижения науки и образования*, (5 (59)), 9-12.